

ARETE PILOT 1

Using Augmented Reality to facilitate teaching English literacy skills

What is this pilot about?

Aiming to make both teaching and learning English language literacy more accessible and successful for those teachers and children engaged in the process, Pilot 1 is expected to be delivered to students in four or more countries. The online WordsWorthLearning literacy programme (WWL) embraces clinical, educational, social and political solutions to the cycle of illiteracy.

240 students

2 groups

The WWL-AR group uses the AR app developed by WWL, and separately, the Control group proceeds as normal.

The outcome

With a redesigned AR app to accommodate better UI/UX functionalities and operational performance focusing on Augmented Reality content, ARETE introduces gamification with additional adaptive learning functionalities. WWL-AR apps are developed with a technology for “markerless” AR which enhances the user’s interaction and perception of the real world.

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AR in Education

ARETE aims to:

- **develop, integrate and disseminate** interactive technology via AR methods building a pan-European competitive ecosystem.
- **strengthen the research and industrial capacities** in Europe to develop future interactive devices and content for education.
- support the existing effort to seek opportunities offered by **multi-user interactions with AR technologies in education.**

Within the three pilot studies, ARETE evaluates the effectiveness and impact of disruptive AR in education.

The ARETE Project Pilot 1 will redevelop an existing WordsWorthLearning (WWL) digital programme into an app containing Augmented Reality (AR).

WWL was developed by a Consulting Speech Language Therapist with over 30 years clinical experience and who is a specialist in resolving specific learning difficulties, including dyslexia.

ARETE PARTNERS

